

Interreg

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Alpine Space

Forest EcoValue

AWARENESS RAISING ACTIONS

D.3.3.2

RESPONSIBLE PARTNER: LGCA (LOMBARDY GREEN
CHEMISTRY ASSOCIATION) / PP7

Interreg Alpine Space Programme 21-27

Carbon neutral and resource sensitive Alpine region

SO 2.2: Promoting the transition to a circular and resource efficient economy

Forest EcoValue:

Supporting multiple forest ecosystem services through new circular/green/bio markets and value chains

Project ID: ASP0100005

List of the Forest EcoValue project partners

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- PP2. Lombardy Foundation for the Environment – Fondazione Lombardia per l’Ambiente [FLA]
- PP4. National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment – Institut National de Recherche pour l’Agriculture, l’Alimentation et l’Environnement [INRAE]
- PP5. Slovenia Forest Service – Zavod za Gozdove Slovenije [ZGS]
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- PP8. University of Graz, Institute of Environmental Systems Sciences [UNIGRAZ]
- PP9. Regional Centre for Forest Property Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes – Centre Régional de la Propriété Forestière [CNPF]
- PP10. The French National Forest Office – Office National des Forêts [ONF]
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Glossary

AG – Action Group (within EUSALP framework)

ASP – Alpine Space Programme

CNPF – Centre National de la Propriété Forestière

CO₂ – Carbon dioxide

EUSALP – EU Strategy for the Alpine Region

FES – Forest Ecosystem Services

FLA – Fondazione Lombardia per l’Ambiente

FINPIE – Finpiemonte SpA

HCS – Holzcluster Steiermark

IFUPLAN – Institut für Umweltplanung und Raumentwicklung GmbH & Co. KG

INRAE – Institut National de Recherche pour l’Agriculture, l’Alimentation et l’Environnement

LL – Living Lab

LGCA – Lombardy Green Chemistry Association

NTFPs – Non-Timber Forest Products

ONF – Office National des Forêts

PP – Project Partner

PPP – Public–Private Partnership

TG – Target Group

UNIGRAZ – University of Graz

ZGS – Zavod za Gozdove Slovenije (Slovenia Forest Service)

1. Introduction

Awareness-raising actions are central to the Forest EcoValue mission. They ensure that knowledge and outputs generated within the project reaches key stakeholders, from policymakers and forest managers to local communities and the wider public. By disseminating results, building capacity, and fostering dialogue across borders, these actions aim to strengthen the recognition of Alpine forests as strategic resources, while encouraging the adoption of innovative approaches to forest management and ecosystem service markets.

According to the project application form, awareness raising is not limited to communication at local and regional level but extends strategically to the European context. All project partners contributed to the joint objective of actively promoting Forest EcoValue outputs in at least three relevant EU-level international events. This coordinated effort ensures that the project's concepts and tested models are "satellited" beyond the Alpine region, reaching potential replicators in other European territories facing similar ecological and economic challenges.

The project disseminates transferable tools, business models, and policy recommendations that can inspire replication and scaling-up across Europe. In this way, awareness-raising activities not only support the uptake of project results but also reinforce Forest EcoValue's transnational added value, ensuring that the lessons learned in the Alpine Living Labs resonate far beyond their original territories.

Among the outputs promoted through awareness-raising activities there are:

1. **Transnational network of 5 Living Labs** (Output 2.1): Living Labs in five Alpine countries serve as testing sites for forest ecosystem service (FES) market frameworks and payment schemes. They are practical demonstration cases that can inspire replication elsewhere.
2. **Transnational guidelines and tools** (Output 2.2): practical, multi-lingual guidelines and tools for establishing and managing public-private markets for selected FES in Alpine communities. These provide concrete methods and governance models applicable across regions.
3. **Regional feasibility assessments** (Output 2.3): assessments based on Living Lab results, highlighting conditions for effective FES markets in different Alpine territories, with recommendations for replication.
4. **Regional Roadmaps** (Output 2.4): next-step action plans, co-drafted with stakeholders in each Living Lab, which outline how to continue implementing FES markets and new value chains after the project ends.
5. **Policy Memo** (Output 3.1): recommendations for policy improvements to enable or facilitate FES markets, payment schemes, and forest-based value chains in the Alpine region. This is particularly relevant for EU-level policy discussions.
6. **Online Training Modules** (Output 3.2): e-learning materials designed to build capacity among stakeholders (e.g. forest owners, SMEs, local authorities) on FES valuation, business models, and market creation.

Project partners contributed to awareness-raising by presenting and discussing Forest EcoValue results at international events of European relevance, as well as by disseminating targeted information to relevant bodies and action groups within the Alpine Convention and EUSALP networks through various channels (emails, technical meetings, etc). These occasions offered an important opportunity to engage with

researchers, policymakers and practitioners working on mountain ecosystems, climate adaptation and sustainable forest management.

In particular:

- the Slovenia Forest Service (SFS) presented the results and outputs of Forest EcoValue at the **International Mountain Conference 2025**, addressing the role of forest ecosystem services in mountain regions and their contribution to risk mitigation and recreational functions. The intervention aimed to raise awareness on the role of forest ecosystem services in mountain areas, disseminate project-related knowledge to an international audience, and strengthen the uptake of project results within scientific, policy and transnational networks.
- INRAE participated in the **EUSALP Annual Forum 2025**, where project results and policy recommendations were presented within a workshop dedicated to climate change adaptation in the Alpine region. This participation helped increase the visibility of Forest EcoValue among EU-level stakeholders and policy actors.
- Finpiemonte had the opportunity to present the key outputs of the Forest EcoValue project at the **2026 Annual Meeting of the Permanent Committee of the Alpine Convention**, having been selected by the Italian Ministry of Environment and Energy Security (MASE) and Regione Piemonte. This provided an important opportunity to bring the project results into a high-level Alpine governance forum and to connect them with ongoing policy discussions.

Finally, the Forest EcoValue Final Conference, held on 26 March 2026 in Turin (Italy) at the headquarters of Regione Piemonte, represented the main concluding dissemination event of the project. Organised as a side event of the Alpine Convention Permanent Committee meeting, it ensured strong institutional visibility and direct engagement with key Alpine and EU-level stakeholders.

Through these transnational events, the consortium contributed to disseminating project results beyond the Alpine Living Labs and to strengthening dialogue at European level on forest ecosystem services and sustainable forest management.

2. Project overview

Forests of the Alpine Space play a key role in climate change mitigation and resilience, providing multiple ecosystem services (ES) and environmental and social benefits such as CO₂ absorption, air pollution reduction, biodiversity enhancement, and protection against natural hazards. However, they are threatened by abandonment, climate change, and territorial degradation, which progressively reduce natural resources and the provision of forest ES (FES). Maintenance costs of Alpine forests are high, and public funds and traditional wood value chains are insufficient to cover them. Economic valuation and payment schemes for FES are widely discussed but rarely successfully applied.

The Forest EcoValue project addresses this challenge by developing innovative, sustainable business models for forest management and maintenance, supporting new bio-based value chains and ES markets, and involving different sectors, public and private actors, and citizens. Restoring and maintaining healthy

forests has been recognised as a source of value for the Alpine region, while also creating business opportunities and green jobs for Alpine communities.

The project focuses on a subset of FES from the following categories:

1. **Provisioning** (e.g. biomass, raw materials, chemicals) with a specific focus on non-timber forest products, and on the production of woody biomass for energy, integrated into circular energy markets.
2. **Regulating** (e.g. biodiversity, natural risk reduction, CO₂ absorption) concretely working on carbon and biodiversity credits, natural risk management through protective forests, and innovative environmental finance instruments such as green bonds and reverse auctions.
3. **Cultural** (e.g. recreation, habitat experience, health) particularly enhancing recreational and tourism services and spiritual and cultural services.

These services have been explored and tested within Living Labs (LLs) across five countries, located in different Alpine territories and representing diverse ecological and socio-economic contexts:

1. **Italy – Valle Tanaro, Piedmont:** The LL in Valle Tanaro explores innovative approaches to valorising chestnut groves, promoting non-timber forest products, developing carbon and biodiversity credits, and fostering experiential activities linked to forest and rural heritage.
2. **France - Haute-Savoie:** Grand Anney and Thonon LLs focus respectively on two aspects: 1) recreational ecosystem services, enhancing the value of forests through the sale of experiences such as ecotourism, outdoor activities, and educational programmes; 2) enhancing the value of water regulation services through a public-private partnership.
3. **Slovenia – Karavanke Mountains, municipality Tržič:** The Slovenian LL addresses natural risk management with a focus on torrent control, advances solutions for wood biomass supply chains and promotes sustainable tourism and recreational use of forests.
4. **Austria – Province of Styria:** The Styrian LL concentrates on biodiversity and habitat provision and carbon sequestration and storage through innovative financing mechanisms such as reverse auctions.
5. **Germany – Tegernsee Valley, Upper Bavaria:** The German LL explores spiritual and cultural services, such as forest cemeteries with biodegradable urns, while also fostering habitat and biodiversity conservation through collaborative public-private partnerships.

Accordingly, the project is aiming to:

1. Map and analyse the Alpine Space forests delivery capacity of FES;
2. Identify and estimate the economic potential, define business models and FES market frameworks;
3. Test the models/tools developed by the consortium in pilot LLs involving local players;
4. Compare results at transnational level, identifying obstacles and facilitating factors;

5. Analyse the need for innovative policies to foster forest maintenance, FES markets, and new value chains;
6. Elaborate refined transferable tools/models and policy proposals to enable new markets and value chains and ensure the expected FES.

Throughout the project, a continuous participatory process is carried out within the Living Labs. Stakeholders' active involvement in these labs is essential for co-designing and testing models and tools, ensuring that the innovative approaches are rooted in local realities. In parallel, public events and capacity-building workshops have strengthened engagement, supported knowledge transfer, and provided regular updates on project activities. This participatory and long-term approach, tested across the five territories, is paving the way for refined, transferable tools and policy proposals that can unlock new markets and value chains while safeguarding the provision of ecosystem services in the Alpine Space.

Project duration: 42 months

3. Summary table on Awareness raising actions

Event	Level	Date	Format	TGs reached
<i>International Mountain Conference</i>	Transnational	14-19.09.2025	In person	TG17, TG18, TG19
<i>EUSALP Annual Forum</i>	EU	25-26.11.2025	In person	TG1, TG2, TG4, TG5, TG7, TG10, TG11, TG12, TG17, TG18, TG19
<i>Alpine Convention Permanent Committee meeting</i>	EU	26.03.2026	In person	TG19
<i>Forum Alpinum 2026</i>	EU	28-30.05.2026	In person	TBD
<i>Alpine Convention Workshop on Innovative Mountain</i>	Transnational	04.05.2026	Online	TBD

<i>Agriculture and Forestry</i>				
<i>EU Green Week 2026</i>	EU	02.06.2026	n/a	TBD

4. Description of each awareness raising action

Slovenia Forest Service (SFS) – Participation at the International Mountain Conference

The Slovenia Forest Service (SFS) participated in the International Mountain Conference, held from 14 to 19 September 2025 (onsite event). The conference brought together a broad international community of researchers and practitioners working on mountain ecosystems, sustainable development, climate adaptation, and natural risk management. Within this framework, SFS presented two scientific contributions: *“Mitigating torrential risks in mountainous regions through forest management: a case study from Slovenia”* and *“Importance of mountain forest for leisure activities – the case of the municipality of Tržič, Slovenia”*.

The first presentation focused on the role of forest management practices in mitigating torrential and hydrogeological risks in mountainous regions, providing practical evidence from the Slovenian case study. The second addressed the multifunctional value of mountain forests, highlighting their contribution to leisure activities and local socio-economic development. Through these contributions, SFS aimed to raise awareness on the importance of forest ecosystem services in mountain areas, particularly in the context of climate change adaptation, risk reduction, and sustainable territorial development.

Although the high number of parallel sessions makes it difficult to estimate the total number of conference attendees, the event ensured visibility among a wide international audience.

Target groups reached:

- **TG17 – Higher education and research organisations**, actively engaged in scientific exchange and policy-relevant research on mountain forestry, climate risks, and ecosystem services.
- **TG18 – Transnational organisations** (such as Alpe Adria, Arge Alp, etc.), which play a key role in policy framework analysis and preparation of policy proposals. These actors can disseminate project solutions to their members at transnational level, act as multipliers, and contribute as observers or facilitators in specific actions (e.g., Living Labs).
- **TG19 – Alpine Convention bodies** (Mountain Agriculture and Forestry Working Group, Alpine Climate Board, Alpine Biodiversity Board, Natural Hazards Working Group) and **EUSALP Action Groups** (AG2 – Economic potential of strategic sectors; AG6 – Preservation and valorisation of natural resources; AG8 – Risk management and climate change adaptation). These bodies can directly integrate and mainstream project results into their ongoing work and disseminate findings to mountain areas beyond the Living Labs.

In terms of awareness raising beyond the event itself, SFS disseminated information about its participation through a dedicated post on the Slovenia Forest Service Facebook page on 19 September, targeting both forestry professionals and the general public. This social media outreach expanded the visibility of the project outcomes and reinforced engagement beyond the conference audience.

Media presence: Information about the Slovenia Forest Service's participation in the International Mountain Conference was disseminated to both the general public and the forestry sector through an official post published on the Slovenia Forest Service Facebook page on 19 September. The post presented the titles and focus of the two contributions delivered at the conference, highlighting the relevance of forest ecosystem services in mountainous areas and their role in risk mitigation and recreational functions. A screenshot of the Facebook post is attached below as supporting evidence of the dissemination activity.

Figure 1. LinkedIn post on SFS (PP5) page related to the participation at the International Mountain Conference

INRAE – Participation at the EUSALP Annual Forum 2025

INRAE participated in the EUSALP Annual Forum, held on 25–26 November 2025 in Innsbruck, within the AG8 workshop entitled “*Enhancing Climate Change Adaptation through cross-project policy recommendations and pilot actions in the Alps*”. The workshop was jointly organised by AG8 together with the INTERREG projects ADAPTNOW, X-Risk-CC, MOSAIC, and Forest EcoValue. Its main objective was to strengthen the adaptation capacities of regional and local authorities in the Alpine region, taking into account the complexity of multi-level governance systems. The workshop aimed to identify common action fields, develop shared policy recommendations, and showcase exemplary pilot initiatives to advance climate change adaptation at Alpine scale.

Within this framework, INRAE delivered a 10-minute presentation entitled “*From a Web Atlas on Climate Compound Events to a Policy Brief Supporting Forest Ecosystem Services: Insights from the MOSAIC, ADAPTNOW, and Forest EcoValue Project*”. The presentation highlighted how scientific tools (such as a web-based atlas on climate compound events) and policy-oriented outputs (including the Forest EcoValue policy memo brief) can support evidence-based decision-making and the integration of forest ecosystem services into climate adaptation strategies. A printed version of the Forest EcoValue policy memo brief was made available at the AG8 corner; all 50 printed copies were distributed by the end of the two-day event, demonstrating strong interest from participants.

The workshop registered 69 participants, with 32 attending the AG8 session (TG1, TG2, TG4, TG5, TG7, TG10, TG11, TG12, TG17, TG18, TG19). The audience included representatives of public administrations, regional and local authorities, research centres and universities, climate agencies, the Interreg Alpine Space Joint Secretariat, the Danube Strategy, the European Commission, the Alpine Convention, as well as experts and practitioners. A dedicated panel discussion further fostered dialogue on the role of EUSALP and transnational cooperation in scaling up local solutions and enhancing policy preparedness for climate risk management.

In terms of awareness raising and dissemination, the event facilitated networking opportunities among policymakers, researchers, and EU-level representatives, strengthening the policy relevance and visibility of the project.

Photos documenting INRAE’s participation in the EUSALP Annual Forum and the AG8 workshop are provided below this section as supporting evidence of the awareness-raising activity and stakeholder engagement.

Figure 2. Photo related to INRAE's participation at the EUSALP Annual Forum 2025

Figure 3. Photo related to INRAE's participation at the EUSALP Annual Forum 2025

Finpiemonte – Presentation at the Annual Meeting 2026 of the Permanent Committee of the Alpine Convention

Finpiemonte, selected by the Italian Ministry of Environment and Energy Security (MASE) and Regione Piemonte, presented the key outputs of the Forest EcoValue project at the Annual Meeting 2026 of the Permanent Committee of the Alpine Convention, held in the morning of March 26th.

The presentation provided an overview of the project rationale, highlighting the need to recognise and support the multiple values generated by Alpine forests through an integrated approach to forest ecosystem services. It introduced the methodological framework developed by the project, combining ecological assessment, economic valuation and territorial implementation through the network of five Living Labs.

Particular attention was given to the practical tools produced by the project, the lessons learned from pilot implementation, and the recommendations developed to support governance frameworks such as the Alpine Convention and EUSALP.

The intervention attracted strong interest and generated extensive feedback from representatives of several Alpine countries, confirming the relevance of the project themes within the Alpine policy debate. Some participants subsequently joined the Final Conference in order to receive further insights and deepen the discussion on project results.

All Project Partners – Forest EcoValue Final Conference

Figure 4. Photos related to the Final Conference

The Forest EcoValue Final Conference, held on 26 March 2026 in Turin (Italy), at the headquarters of Regione Piemonte, represented a key transnational awareness-raising event, marking the culmination of the project's activities and providing a strategic platform to disseminate its main results to a broad audience of stakeholders at Alpine and European level. Organised in the framework of the Alpine Convention Permanent Committee meeting, the event ensured high international visibility and strong institutional engagement, reinforcing the policy relevance of the project outcomes.

Participation in the conference (64 participants) was ensured through a combination of targeted and open dissemination actions. Invitations were circulated both through direct outreach to relevant stakeholders and through a dedicated LinkedIn communication campaign. Registrations were collected via an online registration form, allowing for an efficient organisation of participants and contributing to broadening the audience beyond the immediate project network.

The conference gathered a diverse audience including policymakers, representatives of regional and national authorities, research institutions, project partners, and stakeholders involved in forest management, ecosystem services, and sustainable value chains. The participation of representatives from the Alpine Convention and EUSALP further strengthened the link between project results and ongoing policy processes at transnational level.

The agenda was structured to provide a comprehensive overview of the project's achievements and their practical implications. The event opened with the institutional welcome by the Regional Minister for Mountain and Territorial Development of Regione Piemonte, complemented by a video message from the Alpine Space Project Officer, who provided greetings and expressed appreciation for the work carried out by the consortium. This introduction was followed by the presentation of the Forest EcoValue vision, key challenges, and methodological approach by the Project Coordinator.

Subsequent sessions focused on the core thematic areas of the project. Scientific insights on forest ecosystem services and their policy relevance were presented, highlighting the importance of integrating these services into decision-making processes. This was complemented by presentations on the economic valuation of forest ecosystem services and the development of innovative business models, demonstrating how environmental benefits can be translated into sustainable market opportunities.

A dedicated session illustrated how the Living Labs contributed to the co-creation and testing of solutions, leading to the development of concrete roadmaps for future implementation. In addition, territorial experiences from pilot areas were presented, showcasing the added value generated at local level and the transferability potential of the project results across the Alpine region.

The conference also featured a roundtable discussion with external stakeholders, including representatives from the Alpine Convention and EUSALP, focusing on how to scale up forest ecosystem services from scientific approaches to practical applications. This session fostered dialogue on policy integration, replication potential, and the role of transnational cooperation in supporting sustainable forest management.

The conference also generated active interaction with the audience through questions and requests for further clarification from participants. The discussion confirmed the strong interest in the project results, particularly regarding the practical applicability of the tools developed, the transferability of the Living Lab experiences, and the policy implications for Alpine territories.

The event concluded with closing remarks summarising the key messages and future perspectives, emphasising the importance of continuing collaboration beyond the project's lifetime.

Overall, the Final Conference played a crucial role in consolidating project results, enhancing their visibility, and promoting their uptake among key stakeholders. It contributed to strengthening the transnational dialogue on forest ecosystem services and sustainable value chains, while supporting the integration of Forest EcoValue outcomes into policy frameworks and future initiatives in the Alpine region. Photos documenting the Final Conference are provided below this section as supporting evidence of the awareness-raising activity and stakeholder engagement.

Figure 5. Photo related to the Final Conference

Figure 6. Photo related to the Final Conference

Figure 7. Photo related to the Round Table discussion held during the Final Conference

Figure 8. Photo related to the presentation by Victoria Yavorskaya (UniGraz) on the economic valuation of forest ecosystem services held during the Final Conference

Media presence: The Final Conference was supported by a well-structured communication approach that ensured solid media visibility before, during, and after the event. Information about the conference was shared through targeted outreach activities aimed at both specialised stakeholders and a broader audience, helping to boost engagement during the registration phase and increase overall exposure. Shortly after the event, a LinkedIn post published on 27 March 2026 highlighted the main outcomes, complemented by additional posts shared by project partners both ahead of and following the conference, further extending its reach across different networks.

Media coverage was also reinforced by Finpiemonte, which issued a press release and compiled a press review; these materials are accessible through the news article published on its website (<https://www.finpiemonte.it/progetti-strategici/conferenza-finale-del-progetto-il-materiale-condiviso>). The same page also provides access to the presentations delivered during the conference, making it easier to share the project results with a wider audience beyond those who attended. More detailed information on the communication activities related to the Final Conference will be included in Deliverable D.3.3.4.

FLA (PP2) - Participation of in Forum Alpinum 2026

As part of the FEV project’s transnational awareness-raising activities, FLA (PP2) will participate in Forum Alpinum 2026, a major Alpine-wide science–policy event organised by the International Scientific Committee on Research in the Alps (ISCAR), taking place in Aosta (Italy) from 28 to 30 May 2026. The forum is expected to bring together researchers, policymakers and practitioners to address key environmental, socio-economic and governance challenges affecting Alpine regions in the context of climate change, with a particular focus on adaptation, resilience and sustainable development.

Within this context, FLA will present a poster based on the FEV project, entitled “Can Forest ecosystem services attract private finance? A Bankability Index for Alpine investment projects”. The contribution will introduce the Bankability Index as a transparent tool designed to assess and communicate the financial risk, robustness and policy dependence of forest ecosystem service business models, while also fostering dialogue among ecologists, forest managers and financial institutions at the transnational Alpine level.

INRAE – Participation in an Alpine Convention Workshop on Innovative Mountain Agriculture and Forestry

As part of the projects’ outreach and knowledge-sharing activities, participation is also foreseen in an upcoming event at Alpine level. On 4 May 2026, the Alpine Convention will host an online workshop on Innovative Mountain Agriculture and Forestry, in which both MOSAIC and Forest EcoValue will contribute by presenting their innovative products and approaches.

INRAE - Participation in EU Green Week 2026

In addition, INRAE has been invited by the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region to represent both projects at the 26th edition of EU Green Week on 2 June 2026, within the Partners’ Events programme. This year’s edition will focus on the business case for nature, highlighting how a nature-positive economy can support Europe’s prosperity, resilience and competitiveness.

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